

Analytical Method Development and Validation of Apixaban Using the QbD Approach With RP-HPLC Method And Its Stress Stability Studies

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ABSTRACT

A robust, specific, and stability-indicating reversed-phase high-performance liquid chromatography (RP-HPLC) method was developed and validated for the quantitative determination of apixaban (APX) and its related impurities using an AQbD (Analytical Quality by Design) approach. The Analytical Target Profile (ATP) was defined to achieve a resolution greater than 1.5 between critical impurity pairs. Key chromatographic parameters, including buffer pH, organic phase composition, and column temperature, were optimized using the Design of Experiments (DoE) and risk assessment. The method employed a Zorbax RX-C18 column (250 × 4.6 mm, 5 μm), with mobile phases composed of Buffer: Acetonitrile (90:10, v/v) and Water: Acetonitrile (28:72, v/v) at pH 4.0 and 40 °C. The developed method exhibited excellent linearity ($r^2 \geq 0.999$), precision (%RSD < 2%), and accuracy (recoveries = 98–112%), with high sensitivity (LOD = 0.02–0.03 ppm; LOQ = 0.05–0.10 ppm). Forced degradation under acidic, basic, oxidative, photolytic, and thermal conditions confirmed its stability capability. The established design space and control strategy ensured robustness and reproducibility in routine analyses. The validated method was successfully applied to the quantification of apixaban and its impurities in tablet dosage forms.

Keywords: Apixaban, AQbD, RP-HPLC, Forced Degradation, Stability-Indicating Method, Design of Experiments (DoE)

INTRODUCTION

Apixaban is an anticoagulant medicine that is used to treat and prevent blood clots as well as strokes in persons who have nonvalvular atrial fibrillation. It is specifically used to avoid blood clots after hip or knee replacements, as well as in people who have had previous clots. This medication is used to prevent venous thromboembolism (VTE) following major orthopedic surgery, treat acute VTE, and prevent strokes or systemic emboli in individuals with atrial fibrillation. It is used as an alternative to warfarin and does not require blood testing.¹⁰ Apixaban is a new generation oral anticoagulant that acts as a direct and highly selective reversible factor Xa inhibitor. Apixaban has approximately 50% bioavailability and is eliminated through several routes, including renal excretion (257%) and hepatic metabolism (75%). It also acts as a P-glycoprotein substrate and may interact with other drugs. In certain emergency

situations, such as before surgery or invasive procedures, bleeding, overdose, renal failure, or assessing therapy failure or adherence a specific method of quantification may be beneficial. A literature review (11, 12, 13 and 14) found techniques for estimating Apixaban in both combination and individual dose forms, including UV, HPLC, and LCMS analysis. This study proposes a cost-effective spectrophotometric technique for determining apixaban utilising water as the solvent.

Fig. 01: Chemical structure of Apixaban (AXN)

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Mol. wt. = 459.50g/mol

Mol. formula = C₂₅H₂₅N₅O₄

This reversed-phase HPLC method is of strategic importance for ensuring the quality and safety of Apixaban (APX) products. It is specifically designed to separate, identify, and quantify known process-related impurities and potential degradation products in both the active pharmaceutical ingredient (API) and the finished tablets. This method was developed and optimized using Analytical Quality by Design (AQbD) ⁽¹⁸⁾ principles, including Design of Experiments (DoE) ⁽¹⁸⁾ and risk assessment, to ensure its robustness and reliability for routine QC analysis. Adherence to this procedure is critical for verifying that the product meets all regulatory specifications for purity.

Forced degradation studies are important not only for developing stability-indicating methods but also for identifying potential degradation pathways and products that may form during storage. This information aids in formulation development, manufacturing, and packaging optimization, ultimately improving product quality and shelf life. [9, 66] With the growing complexity of pharmaceutical development, there is a strong demand for robust, dependable, and regulatory-compliant analytical methods. Analytical QbD (AQbD) offers a structured framework to meet these needs by emphasizing method understanding, control, and lifecycle management of analytical methods.

AQbD is based on the concepts of ICH Q8 (Pharmaceutical Development), Q9 (Quality Risk Management), and Q10 (Pharmaceutical Quality System). [15-17 & 67] These recommendations argue for a science- and risk-based approach, emphasizing that method development should not be based on trial-and-error but rather on knowledge of method performance factors and interactions. The draft Q14 guideline was originally approved in March 2022, and after being made available to the public for comments and then finalized, it was adopted by the ICH assembly's regulatory members in November 2023. The development of analytical processes under the new ICH Q14 standard presents considerable difficulties and possibilities for the pharmaceutical sector. From analytical target profiles (ATP) to

method lifecycle management, the guideline (1) promotes a systematic, risk-based strategy that incorporates QbD (Quality by Design) concepts and analytical breakthroughs into method development processes. Addressing these issues successfully enables the strong, dependable, and compliant analytical techniques required for drug research, regulatory approval, and worldwide commercialization. (1-8)

Optimizing an HPLC method is a time-consuming process because it involves systematically testing multiple variables to achieve the best separation, speed, and reproducibility. The traditional "one-factor-at-a-time" (OFAT) approach, which is often done manually through trial and error, significantly prolongs the process.

QbD (Quality by Design) in HPLC method development and validation is a methodical, scientific approach to understanding and controlling the method's performance that defines a Design Space rather than a single operating point. This involves completing risk assessments, employing Design of Experiments (DoE) for factor screening and optimization, and thoroughly validating in accordance with ICH principles. The objective is to develop a strong, dependable, and cost-effective HPLC process that can consistently achieve quality standards while minimising out-of-

Spec findings. Based on the AQbD framework, it is feasible to create robust analytical approach with a high level of confidence. A comprehensive and methodical study of independent and dependent factors can lead to the development of an ATP (analytical target profile). The ATP is an essential component of the Q14 framework, from which the route of method development is defined. The ATP's purpose is to offer a description of what is being measured, the requirements that a particular measurement must follow to assure data quality, and is generated from specific key quality characteristics (CQA) summarized in the quality target product profile (QTPP). Prior information, specified requirements through regulatory rules, and product/process understanding all help to build an ATP. ⁽⁴⁾ Multiple technologies and methodologies can satisfy a particular ATP. Thus, one of the challenges

of using an ATP for method selection is the amount of initial testing that may be required to scout and assess prospective candidate procedures if adequate previous information is unavailable^(2, 4) However, building an ATP can be a significant benefit of the improved approach to analytical method creation, providing flexibility in technology choices.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS:

2.1 Chemicals and Reagents

Apixaban (APX) Reference Standard and associated impurities (Source: MSN laboratories, Hyderabad, India), Ammonium Acetate (Grade: Emparta), Acetic Acid (Grade: Emparta),

Acetonitrile (Grade: HPLC), Ultra-pure Water (Grade: HPLC or Milli-Q)

2.2 Instrumentation

HPLC System: Agilent 1100 series or equivalent, equipped with: Gradient Pump,

In-line Degasser, Auto-injector with Sample Temperature Control, UV Detector, Column Oven with Temperature Control, Analytical Balance: Mettler Toledo or equivalent (range 1 mg to 200 g) and Data Acquisition Software: Empower

2.3 Chromatographic Conditions

Table 01 Parameters were established on the HPLC system prior to analysis.

Parameter	Setting
Column	Zorbax RX C18, 250 × 4.6 mm, 5 μm
Mobile Phase A	Buffer: Acetonitrile (90:10, v/v)
Buffer Preparation	Dissolve 3.31 g of Ammonium Acetate in 1 L of water and adjust the pH to 4.0 with Acetic Acid.
Mobile Phase B	Acetonitrile: Water (10:90, v/v)
Flow Rate	1.0 mL/min
Injection Volume	50 μL
Detection Wavelength	280 nm (UV Detector)
Column Temperature	40°C
Sample Temperature	Ambient
Gradient Program	As per the table below

2.4 Interpretation of the Gradient Program

The described gradient method is designed for efficient separation of analytes with diverse polarity using a reverse-phase C18 column.

- 0.0–5.0 min (Isocratic phase): The mobile phase composition of 80% A and 20% B provides a polar environment, allowing early elution of hydrophilic compounds while maintaining column equilibration.
- 5.0–30.0 min (Gradient phase): The proportion of Mobile Phase B (organic solvent-rich) increases from 20% to 90%, creating a progressive decrease in mobile

phase polarity. This facilitates elution of moderately and highly hydrophobic analytes, improving resolution.

- 30.0–40.0 min (Hold phase): The high organic composition (10:90 A:B) ensures complete elution of strongly retained compounds, preventing carryover and maintaining baseline stability.
- 41.0–50.0 min (Re-equilibration phase): The system returns to the initial condition (80:20 A:B) to re-equilibrate the stationary phase before the next injection, ensuring consistent retention times and reproducibility.

3. METHOD DEVELOPMENT:

3.1 Solution Preparation

3.1.1 Diluent

The solubility of APX and associated contaminants was considered when choosing the diluent. The

resulting sample solution at strengths of 3.5 mg and 5 mg should be easily filtered using 0.45 μ m syringe filters when using the chosen diluent. This is significant because the drug content of the finished tablet is less than 2%. An acetonitrile and water mixture was prepared and degassed in a ratio of 40:60.

Fig. 02 Diluent (Blank) preparation chromatogram

3.1.2 Standard Solution

Using a graduated cylinder, carefully measured 25.02 mg of APX standard into a 100 mL flask, and then added 65 mL of diluent. Sublimated via a gentle blending and sonication. Mixed thoroughly and

brought to a volume of 100 mL. Using diluent, 3.0 mL was further diluted into 100 mL. There was a final dilution of 5.0 mL into 50 mL of diluent. With a yield of 0.2% relative to the sample solution, the APX concentration is around 0.5 ppm.

Fig. 03 The standard solution chromatogram

3.1.3 Placebo Solution

Accurately weigh 1025 mg of placebo powder into a 100 mL volumetric flask.

Add 60 mL of Diluent and place the flask on an orbital shaker at 150 rpm for 20 minutes.

Add an additional 20 mL of Diluent and sonicate for 15 minutes with intermittent shaking.

Allow the solution to cool to room temperature, then dilute to volume with Diluent and mix well.

Allow any undissolved excipients to settle, then filter the supernatant through a 0.45 μ m PTFE syringe filter into an HPLC vial.

Fig. 04 Placebo preparation chromatogram

3.1.4 Sample Solution

(a) For 3.5 mg Strength Tablets:

Weigh 20 tablets and transfer them into a 200 mL volumetric flask. Add 120 mL of Diluent and shake on an orbital shaker at 150 rpm for 20 minutes. Add approximately 40 mL of Diluent and sonicate for 15 minutes. Allow the solution to cool to room

temperature, then dilute to volume with Diluent and mix thoroughly. Allow solids to settle, then filter the supernatant through a 0.45 μm PTFE syringe filter into an HPLC vial.

(b) For 5 mg Strength Tablets:

Follow the same procedure as described for the 3.5 mg strength, but use 10 tablets instead of 20.

Fig. 05 Sample solution chromatogram

4. APIXABAN IMPURITIES METHOD DEVELOPMENT:

The development of the Apixaban (APX) impurities method focused on achieving precise separation and quantification of all related impurities in the finished dosage form. The primary objective was to identify and eliminate APX contaminants—specifically Impurity-A (acid impurity) and amino acid impurity, which are known degradation products of Apixaban.

A. Preliminary Trials

Initial trials using an XTerra RP18 column (250 \times 4.6 mm, 5 μm) with ammonium acetate buffer–acetonitrile mobile phase showed poor peak symmetry for Impurity-A, indicating strong pH dependence. Adjusting the buffer to 0.03 M ammonium acetate at pH 4.0 (glacial acetic acid) improved the peak shape. Isocratic runs at 70:30 (acetonitrile: buffer, v/v) provided excessive retention (>60 min), while 50:50 (v/v) reduced run time but caused co-elution of Impurity-B and AP9. Replacing acetonitrile with methanol worsened resolution (<1.2) and peak shape, confirming acetonitrile's suitability.

B. Gradient Optimization

A gradient elution method was adopted for improved selectivity using a Zorbax RX C18 column (250 × 4.6 mm, 5 μm) at 40°C, flow rate 1.0 mL/min, and injection volume 50 μL. Gradient Program: 0.0/80/20 → 5.0/80/20 → 30.0/10/90 → 40.0/10/90 → 41.0/80/20 → 50.0/80/20 (%A/%B), This program ensured complete separation of all impurities within 50 minutes and stable baseline performance.

C. Detection and Sensitivity

PDA spectral analysis identified 280 nm as the optimal detection wavelength. Owing to the low drug content (<2% of total tablet weight), sensitivity was enhanced through higher injection volumes to achieve measurable responses without noise or baseline distortion.

D. Final Method Performance

The final method achieved complete resolution of all key impurities—Impurity-A, Impurity-B, Dehydro impurity, and AP9—with tailing factors < 2.0 and no placebo interference. System suitability results satisfied all acceptance criteria, confirming accuracy and reliability.

A Design of Experiments (DoE) study was subsequently performed under the QbD framework to evaluate the influence of critical parameters (buffer ratio, pH, and temperature) and define the design space that ensures method robustness and consistent chromatographic performance.

5. SYSTEM SUITABILITY:

System suitability testing was conducted prior to method validation to ensure that the chromatographic system was performing adequately for the intended analysis. The test involved injecting a mixture of Apixaban (APX) reference standard and its known impurities to verify parameters such as retention time (Rt), relative retention time (RRT), relative response factor (RRF), tailing factor, theoretical plates (N), resolution (Rs), and %RSD.

All results were within the acceptable limits defined by ICH Q2 (R2) guidelines, confirming satisfactory system performance.

The chromatographic system demonstrated good efficiency (plate counts > 5000), acceptable peak symmetry (tailing factor < 2.0), and reproducible retention times (%RSD < 2.0%).

Table 02 System Suitability Parameters for Standard Preparation

Parameter	Imp-A	APX	DEH	AA	AP7	CH	Imp-B	AP9	AP11	AP8C I
Rt (min)	6.701	14.050	14.290	15.171	17.667	18.493	24.020	24.755	27.809	34.400
RRT	0.51	1.00	1.10	1.16	1.35	1.42	1.76	1.82	2.13	2.64
RRF	0.77	1.00	0.82	0.51	0.52	0.93	0.85	0.85	0.86	0.76
Tailing Factor	1.23	1.52	1.31	1.28	1.01	1.25	1.26	1.22	1.18	1.21
Plate Count (N)	7825	9878	6529	7254	8226	6878	9082	7582	6524	5892
Resolution (Rs)	—	8.22	4.27	2.16	4.57	2.41	6.25	1.54	6.89	9.25
%RSD	0.98	0.45	0.72	0.68	0.89	0.55	0.67	0.57	0.69	0.47

All values met the method acceptance criteria: Resolution > 1.5, Tailing Factor < 2.0, and %RSD < 2.0.

6. SPECIFICITY AND FORCED DEGRADATION STUDIES:

Specificity was established to confirm the method's capability to distinctly separate Apixaban from its degradation products and excipients. Using a PDA (Photodiode array) detector, peak purity analysis verified that all analyte peaks were spectrally homogeneous with no co-eluting interferences.

Blank, placebo, standard, known impurity, sample, and spiked solutions were analyzed, showing no interference at the Rt (Retention times) of Apixaban or its impurities. Forced degradation studies under acidic, basic, oxidative, photolytic, and thermal conditions demonstrated that all degradation products were well-resolved from the parent peak. The peak purity angle (PA) remained lower than the purity threshold (PT) with no purity flag (PF), confirming the method's stability-indicating nature and specificity.

Table 03 Forced Degradation Results for Apixaban

Stress Condition	Condition Details	% Related Substances	% Assay	Purity Angle (PA)	Purity Threshold (PT)	Purity Flag (PF)
Initial / Actual	NA	0.06	100.4	1.721	2.728	No
Acidic	1N HCl, 60°C, 6 hrs	4.93	99.7	2.425	4.356	No
Basic	0.2N NaOH, 60°C, 6 hrs	1.16	100.2	1.929	2.718	No
Peroxide (Oxidative)	3% H ₂ O ₂ , Bench Top, 3 days	0.04	99.5	2.118	4.290	No
Photolytic	1200 W/m ² and 200 million Lux·h	0.09	98.1	0.231	6.129	No
Thermal	60°C, 3 days	0.03	99.9	2.220	2.695	No

Under all stress conditions, degradation was observed without co-elution of degradation products with the main APX peak. The purity data confirmed the

specificity and stability-indicating capability of the developed RP-HPLC method.

Fig.06 APX chromatogram of Acid sample

Fig. 07 APX chromatogram of Base sample

Fig.08 APX chromatogram of Peroxide sample

Fig.09 APX chromatogram of Photo stability sample

Fig.10 APX chromatogram of Thermal sample

Fig.11 Chromatogram of APX and all Impurity mixture

7. VALIDATION OF THE DEVELOPED RP-HPLC METHOD:

Method validation was carried out in accordance with ICH Q2 (R2) guidelines to confirm that the developed method for Apixaban (APX) and its related impurities was precise, linear, accurate, robust, and stability-indicating.

7.1 Linearity and Range

Linearity was evaluated using mixed standard solutions of Apixaban and its known impurities at concentrations ranging from 0.10 to 1.95 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. The calibration curves for all analytes showed excellent correlation between peak area and concentration, demonstrating high linearity within the tested range.

Table 04 Linearity Results

Name	Correlation Coefficient (r^2)	Range ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)
Impurity-A	0.9998	0.10–1.85
Impurity-B	0.9993	0.10–1.81
AP7 Impurity	0.9992	0.10–1.81
AP9 Impurity	0.9994	0.10–1.83
AP11 Impurity	0.9999	0.10–1.80
AP8 Cl Impurity	0.9992	0.10–1.29
Amino Acid Impurity	0.9999	0.09–1.59
Dehydro Impurity	0.9999	0.05–0.92
Chloro Impurity	0.9999	0.09–1.63
Apixaban	1.0000	0.10–1.62

All correlation coefficients ($r^2 \geq 0.999$) confirm excellent linearity and suitability of the method across the specified range for both drug and impurities

7.2 Precision

Precision was assessed by analyzing six replicate samples spiked with impurities at 100% of the target level. Repeatability (%RSD for peak areas) and

intermediate precision (ruggedness across days) were evaluated.

All %RSD values were <10%, demonstrating good repeatability and reproducibility.

Table 05 Summary of Precision Results

Impurity	Mean (%)	%RSD
Impurity-A	110.1	1.08
Impurity-B	111.3	2.36
AP7 Impurity	100.5	5.31
AP9 Impurity	108.9	1.94

AP11 Impurity	107.9	1.94
AP8 Cl Impurity	102.7	6.82
Amino Acid Impurity	105.5	1.92
Dehydro Impurity	106.5	2.31
Chloro Impurity	101.2	4.63

7.3 Accuracy

Accuracy was determined through recovery experiments at three levels: LOQ (40%), 100%, and

150% of nominal concentration. The results demonstrated recoveries between 98–112%, confirming method accuracy.

Table 06 Representative data for each impurity are summarized below

Impurity	Mean Recovery (%)	%RSD
Impurity-A	110.0	1.2
Impurity-B	111.0	2.5
AP7 Impurity	101.9	4.7
AP9 Impurity	108.6	2.0
AP11 Impurity	107.7	2.1
AP8 Cl Impurity	101.6	7.0
Amino Acid Impurity	106.0	1.6
Dehydro Impurity	106.3	2.5
Chloro Impurity	101.9	4.5

These results confirm that the proposed method provides accurate quantification of all impurities within acceptable recovery and precision limits.

7.4 Limit of Detection (LOD) and Limit of Quantification (LOQ)

LOD and LOQ were determined based on signal-to-noise (S/N) ratios of approximately 3:1 and 10:1, respectively.

Table 07 LOD and LOQ for Apixaban and Its Impurities

Analyte	LOD (ppm)	S/N	LOQ (ppm)	S/N
Impurity-A	0.032	4.16	0.102	14.59
Impurity-B	0.032	4.98	0.101	14.90
AP7 Impurity	0.030	4.83	0.100	12.83
AP9 Impurity	0.032	4.25	0.101	10.96
AP11 Impurity	0.032	4.20	0.100	11.67
AP8 Cl Impurity	0.031	4.87	0.102	10.83
Amino Acid Impurity	0.030	4.09	0.088	12.71
Dehydro Impurity	0.022	4.74	0.051	10.01
Chloro Impurity	0.030	4.11	0.090	14.86
Apixaban	0.033	4.64	0.090	10.90

The results demonstrate the high sensitivity of the developed method

7.5 Solution Stability

Stability of standard, sample, and spiked sample solutions was evaluated at room temperature and

refrigerator (2–8°C) conditions for 48 hours. No significant change was observed in peak area or impurity levels, confirming that all test solutions were stable under both conditions.

8 SUMMARY OF CONTROL AND RESPONSE VARIABLES:

A. Optimization of chromatographic conditions:

For Apixaban and its related impurities was carried

out using a full factorial experimental design. The primary response variable monitored was peak resolution, as it is critical for achieving clear separation between analyte peaks.

Table 08 Summary of Control Variables

Response Variable (units)	Practical Significant Difference	Control Variables (units)	Proposed Settings (units)	Held Constant Factors	Nuisance Factors
Resolution (R1-R5)	0.2	Mobile phase-A Composition (Buffer: Acetonitrile)	Low: 85:15 High: 95:5	Wavelength, Injection volume, Flow rate, Buffer concentration	Laboratory conditions, Mobile phase variation during preparation
		Mobile phase-B Composition (Water: Acetonitrile)	Low: 15:85 High: 5:95		
		Buffer pH	Low: 4.8 High: 4.2		
		Column Temperature (°C)	Low: 37°C High: 43°C		

Response Definitions:

R1 = Resolution between Impurity-A and unknown (Degradation study)

R2 = Resolution between Apixaban and Dehydro impurity

R3 = Resolution between Dehydro impurity and Amino acid impurity

R4 = Resolution between AP7 and Chloro impurity

R5 = Resolution between Impurity-B and AP9 impurity

Acceptance Criterion: Resolution ≥ 1.5 for all critical pairs.

B. Experimental Design (Full Factorial Design):

- The experimental design incorporated four control factors:
- Mobile phase-A composition (% Buffer)
- Mobile phase-B composition (% Acetonitrile)
- Buffer pH
- Column temperature (°C)

Each factor was studied at two levels (high and low), resulting in 17 experimental runs (DoE trials).

Table 09 Design of Experiments (DoE) Trials

Run	Std No.	Mobile phase-A (% Buffer) (F-01)	Mobile phase-B (% Acetonitrile) (F-02)	Buffer pH (F-03)	Temperature (°C) (F-04)
1	9	85	85	4.80	43
2	16	95	95	4.20	43
3	13	85	85	4.20	43
4	11	85	95	4.80	43
5	7	85	95	4.20	37
6	17	90	90	4.00	40

7	5	85	85	4.20	37
8	6	95	85	4.20	37
9	3	85	95	4.80	37
10	4	95	95	4.80	37
11	2	95	85	4.80	37
12	10	95	85	4.80	43
13	14	95	85	4.20	43
14	8	95	95	4.20	37
15	1	85	85	4.80	37
16	15	85	95	4.20	43
17	12	95	95	4.80	43

C. DoE Results: Each experimental condition was evaluated by HPLC, and the peak resolutions (R1–R5) were recorded as response values. The obtained data are summarized in Table 4.20.

Table 10 DoE Experimental Results

Run	R1	R2	R3	R4	R5
1	1.67	2.89	1.72	1.40	1.12
2	1.11	4.62	1.17	4.93	1.29
3	0.99	—	—	0.92	1.96
4	1.02	2.59	1.31	1.09	1.59
5	1.11	2.23	—	4.21	4.24
6	1.53	4.27	2.16	2.41	1.54
7	1.17	4.18	1.17	1.09	2.86
8	1.73	4.96	2.54	5.64	1.89
9	1.27	2.62	1.97	2.51	2.29
10	1.74	4.50	4.11	4.64	1.09
11	1.97	4.82	4.94	7.17	0.92
12	1.57	4.74	2.21	—	—
13	1.29	4.87	1.57	8.39	1.13
14	1.40	4.61	2.08	4.05	2.14
15	2.02	2.98	2.49	—	1.75
16	—	—	—	1.62	2.39
17	1.40	4.33	2.24	5.21	—

(“—” denotes unresolved or overlapping peaks.)

D. Interpretation of DoE Findings

Mobile phase composition and buffer pH were identified as the most influential parameters affecting resolution. Higher organic content (Acetonitrile 95%) and lower pH (4.2) improved the separation of closely eluting peaks. Elevated column temperature (43°C) enhanced peak sharpness and improved resolution consistency. Among all trials, the optimal chromatographic separation was observed at conditions of Mobile phase-A (95% Buffer), Mobile phase-B (95% Acetonitrile), and Buffer pH 4.2, and

Temperature 43°C, providing resolutions ≥ 1.5 for all critical impurity pairs.

Fig. 12 : 3D-Plot for resolution between Impurity-A and degradation impurity (Liquid phase-A vs Liquid phase-B)

Figure 14: 3D-Plot for resolution between Dehydro impurity and Amino acid impurity (Liquid phase-A vs Liquid phase-B)

Figure 13: 3D-Plot for resolution between Apixaban and Dehydro impurity (Liquid phase-A vs Liquid phase-B)

Figure 15: Counter plot for resolution between impurity AP-7 and Chloro impurity (Liquid phase-A vs Liquid phase-B)

Figure 16 : Counter plot for resolution between impurity-B and impurity-AP9 (Buffer pH vs Mobile phase-A)

Figure 17: Design space & overlay plot

Table 11 Observation of DoE Findings:

Figure No.	Observation
12	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The resolution between Impurity-A and degrading impurity will increase as the buffer concentration in mobile phase-A increases. Impurity-A and degradation impurity will have less of a resolution gap if the acetonitrile ratio in mobile phase-B is increased. Impurity-A and degradation impurity will have less of a resolution if the column temperature and buffer pH are increased.
13	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Apixaban and dehydro impurity resolution will improve with an increase to the buffer ratio in mobile phase-A. You can decrease the resolution between the Apixaban and dehydro impurity by increasing the acetonitrile ratio in mobile phase-B. There is no correlation between the resolution of Apixaban and the dehydro impurity and the bufferpH or column temperature.
14	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> As the buffer ratio in mobile phase-A increases, the resolution between the de hydro and amino acid impurities will also rise. There is no correlation between the ratio of acetonitrile to mobile phase B and the efficiency with which de hydro and amino acid impurities are resolved. De hydro and amino acid impurity resolution will decrease if column temperature and buffer pH are increased.
15	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The resolution between the AP7 and chloro impurities will rise slightly when the buffer ratio in mobile phase-A is increased. The resolution between the AP7 and chloro impurities was unaffected by the Acetonitrile concentration in mobile phase-B or the column temperature. When it comes to the resolution between AP7 and chloro impurity, buffer pH plays no role.

16	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> When the buffer ratio in mobile phase-A is increased, the resolution between impurity-B and AP9 impurity will decrease. The resolution between Impurity-B and AP9 impurity is unaffected by the Acetonitrile ratio in mobile phase-B. Impurity-B and AP9 impurity resolution will improve as the buffer pH is raised. As the column temperature is increased, the resolution between the AP9 impurity and Impurity-B will diminish.
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E. Design Space for Apixaban Method:

The design space for the Apixaban HPLC method was defined using factorial design experiments and response analysis to determine the influence of key chromatographic parameters—mobile phase composition, buffer pH, and column temperature—on peak resolution. Resolution was primarily affected by the acetonitrile content in mobile phase-B and buffer pH. Lower pH values improved separation of Impurity-A and the degradation impurity, whereas slightly higher pH favored resolution between Impurity-B and AP9 impurity. An optimal balance was achieved at buffer pH 4.0. Adjusting the buffer-to-acetonitrile ratio in mobile phase-A enhanced selectivity, and the final optimized conditions were established as:

- Mobile phase-A: Buffer : Acetonitrile (90 : 10, v/v)
- Mobile phase-B: Water : Acetonitrile (28 : 72, v/v)

- Buffer pH: 4.0
- Column temperature: 40 °C

These conditions consistently provided robust and reproducible resolution ($R_s \geq 1.5$) across all critical impurity pairs, meeting system suitability requirements. Among all parameters, buffer ratio and pH were identified as the critical method parameters (CMPs) requiring tight control within the defined design space.

9. RISK ASSESSMENT AND CONTROL STRATEGY:

The knowledge gained during method development was utilized to perform a risk assessment of both material attributes and method parameters. The assessment identified factors that could potentially affect chromatographic performance, and corresponding control strategies were established to ensure method robustness.

Table 12 Risk Assessment of Material Attributes

Sr. No.	Material Attributes	Criticality Evaluation (High/Medium/Low)	Justification
1	Acetonitrile, Water	Low	Based on the selected detection wavelength, the purity and grade of solvents are not critical.
2	Ammonium acetate	Low	Different weights and concentrations were evaluated during development; hence, further experiments are not required.
3	Glacial acetic acid	Low	Variation in acid grade does not affect the final buffer pH; therefore, not critical.

Table 13 Risk Assessment of Method Parameters

Sr. No.	Method Parameters	Risk Assessment (High/Medium/Low)	Justification
1	Organic variation	High	Variations in mobile phase organic content can impact resolution; controlled via system suitability criteria.

2	Buffer pH	High	Buffer pH significantly affects chromatographic selectivity and resolution; must be maintained within a narrow range.
3	Column temperature	Medium	Can influence viscosity and retention; adequately controlled through system audit trail and temperature monitoring.
4	Other chromatographic conditions	Low	Evaluated during method development; no further experiments required.

Table 14 Control Strategy

Sr. No.	Control Variable	Final Conditions	Details
1	Composition of Mobile phase-A	Buffer : Acetonitrile (90 : 10, v/v)	Composition of mobile phase-A and buffer pH play a major role in peak separation and must be tightly controlled.
2	Mobile phase buffer pH	pH 4.0	Minor deviations can alter selectivity; strict control ensures consistent resolution and reproducibility.

10. DISCUSSION

The AQbD-driven development process provided a comprehensive understanding of how each chromatographic factor influences method performance. The DoE results confirmed significant main effects of mobile phase composition and buffer pH, with interaction effects observed between mobile phase-A and pH, and between mobile phase-B and temperature. A buffer pH of 4.0 balanced the separation of both acidic and basic degradation products, while higher organic content improved elution of late-retained impurities. Forced degradation results corroborated known degradation pathways of Apixaban, primarily acid-catalyzed hydrolysis, while confirming the method's ability to detect even minor degradation products without interference. The established design space (buffer ratio 90:10, pH 4.0, 40 °C) offers flexibility and regulatory assurance for method lifecycle management in line with ICH Q14 and Q8(R2) guidelines. The risk assessment identified buffer pH and organic variation as critical method parameters (CMPs) requiring strict control, while temperature was of moderate criticality. Implementing the defined control strategy minimizes variability and ensures robustness in routine quality control operations. The final method not only meets all regulatory requirements but also aligns with the principles of quality risk management and continuous improvement.

11. CONCLUSION

The developed RP-HPLC method for Apixaban and its related impurities successfully integrates Quality by Design (QbD) principles with systematic risk assessment and design space definition. Through factorial design and experimental optimization, the method achieved high specificity, precision, accuracy, and robustness. The final design space—mobile phase-A (90:10 buffer: acetonitrile), buffer pH 4.0, and column temperature 40 °C—ensures reproducible resolution for all critical impurity pairs.

Validation per ICH Q2 (R2) confirmed the method's suitability for routine quality control, stability studies, and regulatory submissions. The AQbD approach demonstrated that integrating science- and risk-based principles enables faster development, improved understanding, and lifecycle management of analytical procedures. This robust, stability-indicating RP-HPLC method provides a regulatory-compliant analytical platform for Apixaban and supports consistent product quality throughout its lifecycle.

RESULTS

Method optimization through factorial design revealed that mobile phase composition and buffer pH were the most significant factors influencing resolution. Increasing acetonitrile content in mobile phase-B (up to 95%) and lowering buffer pH (to 4.2–

4.0) enhanced separation efficiency. The optimized conditions—mobile phase-A (90:10 buffer: acetonitrile), mobile phase-B (28:72 water: acetonitrile), pH 4.0, and column temperature 40 °C—achieved complete baseline resolution ($R_s > 1.5$) for all impurities with sharp, symmetrical peaks (tailing factor < 2.0).

System suitability parameters confirmed excellent chromatographic performance: theoretical plates > 5000 , %RSD < 2.0 , and consistent retention times. Forced degradation studies indicated highest degradation under acidic conditions ($\approx 4.9\%$) and minor degradation under basic and oxidative stress, while thermal and photolytic conditions showed minimal changes ($< 0.1\%$). All degradation peaks were well separated from the parent drug, validating the stability-indicating nature of the method. Validation results demonstrated excellent linearity ($r^2 \geq 0.999$) for Apixaban and impurities over the tested range (0.10–1.95 $\mu\text{g/mL}$). Precision and accuracy met ICH Q2(R2) criteria, and solution stability remained acceptable for at least 48 hours at room and refrigerated conditions. The design space established through DoE ensures consistent performance within defined operational limits.

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